

ZULFIYAKHANIM'S WAY OF LIFE AND CREATIVITY

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ANNOTATION

Life, who has not traveled these roads, but each person has his own life path, his own direction of life and dream of a goal. Some people leave a deep mark on our hearts, and one of those people who left a mark on our hearts is the poetess Zulfiyakhanim. As I describe Zulfiya Khanim's life path, it can be seen that her life was not smooth and that she faced many difficulties in her life.

This article describes the life path of the poetess Zulfiya, some important aspects of her work, various definitions given to her by poets and writers. The scope of themes and the world of images of poetess Zulfia's poems are analyzed. Also, the poetess Zulfia's ability to create a poetic image and poems will be highlighted through analysis. The analysis of Zulfiya's poems shows that the spirit and tone, content and direction, goals, ideas and ideals of his poems are determined by universal thoughts and feelings.

Key words: *poetess, poetry, artistic nature, creativity, literature, unfading memories.*

Zulfia, who was born in the Okhchi neighborhood of Tashkent in a craftsman's family, learned from her father how to relate to work, and from her mother, who loved nature, flowers, and poetry, she heard the poems of Navoi, Bedil, and Fuzuli.

Having discovered the ability to write poetry, Zulfia was afraid that someone would find out about this hobby and laugh at her. In her memoirs, Zulfiya recalls that she wrote poetry as follows: "... I began to think in verses, not in simple phrases as usual... I remembered where I read the lines that sounded inside me and I was able to

remember. At first, I didn't believe that I wrote a poem myself. It was amazing, even a little scary..."

One day, when Zulfiya was still studying at the pedagogical college, a creative meeting with poets and writers of Uzbekistan took place in the assembly hall. Among them were Gafur Ghulam, Mirtemir, Uygun, Izzat Sultan, Hamid Olimjon. One of them was assigned by fate as her husband, adviser, companion, friend. Later, he met others several times in his life and creative path. Zulfia sang about her nation and its centuries-old traditions in her artistic works. In his work, the mother - the keeper of the family hearth - is glorified. A talented poet and writer, a connoisseur of human spiritual impulses, he wrote works of various genres: poems, ballads, elegies, lyric poems, novellas, essays, journalistic articles and newspaper correspondence. Many of his poems are devoted to the struggle for peace and friendship between nations. During the war, he wrote poems in the spirit of patriotism. Together with her husband, Hamid Olimjon, chairman of the Writers' Union, she participates in organizing the lives of writers evacuated from Uzbekistan.

As a public figure, Zulfiya participated in meetings with working people in the regions. In particular, she actively and regularly participated in meetings and conversations with young people in higher educational institutions and schools, in the women's educational institution of pedagogy led by her friend, admirer of the poet's talent, Mehri Sharipovna Sharipova.

Nikolay Tikhonov says about Zulfia: "Her poetry is full of love for life, spirit of freedom, a high sense of the world, the best human feelings. Zulfiya was able to say the dearest word from the bottom of her heart. She shone with a unique light, life was reflected in her incorruptibility of feelings, strict truth, charming lyrics and songs. His words echoed across the cities and fields, he went beyond the borders of his motherland. In Eastern countries - India, Egypt, Vietnam - everywhere they listened to the heart that gave birth to the flame of his poems. She herself is an Eastern woman who illuminates the path of her friends like a new dawn..."

People's poet of Bashkortostan, Mustai Karim, expressed Zulfiya's work very figuratively: "I think about his work. Zulfiya, I think about the earth, about the first soil where these creations found life. Turning to the indelible pages of Alisher Navoi and Zahiriddin Babur, who brought the past and the present together for me, I spent hours thinking and experiencing moments of insight. I deeply study the teachings of Abdulla Qadiri and Oibek, I read the lines of Gafur Ghulam and Hamid Olimjon. There I involuntarily obeyed the call of the trumpet, I was led by the friendly sounds of the trumpet, I was fascinated by the song of either joy or lamentation, I admired the towers piercing the sky. Colors of the earth and sky, ancient wisdom and sounds of the past, eternal labor and sweat flowing through the ditches - all this is Uzbekistan. That's why I asked: "Zulfiya, where did you come to the magical world of poetry?" I won't ask."

Rasul Ghamzatov remembered the name of Zulfiya forever: "...I heard this name for the first time - Zulfiya," the poet remembers when he was studying at the Institute of Literature. "It's like a song, the very name of spring excited me, I had never heard such a name before. I immediately wanted to include this name in some of my poems... Then Zulfiya was mentioned as a poetess and a person. After all, there are beautiful names, but the person himself does not match his name. So, when I learned about Zulfiya, when I met her personally at the writer's convention in Moscow, when I read her poems, I realized that she is a wonderful poetess and a wonderful person, a wonderful woman of the East. Uzbekistan is adequately protected. I will not hide that sometimes we treat women poets with a discount. But Zulfiya turned out to be a poetess whose fate is closely connected with the fate of her people... .. Not only her poems, but also her attitude to her poems examine the poet. I was in his homeland, I traveled with him around Uzbekistan. And I saw how they knew how they loved him. The younger ones called sister Zulfiya, the peers called her sister Zulfiya, and the older ones called her daughter Zulfiya. If you are recognized and honored in your own country, and then your fame spreads throughout the country - this is the happy fate of a poet! His song is loved. They are not only there, in the cotton fields and vineyards, not only under the acacias and maples of Tashkent. His song transcends the language barriers

of soul to soul and finds satisfaction in Poetry. His poetry is light. It teaches love and devotion. He teaches life and word responsibility. It teaches courage to love life, believe in hope for the future."

According to the memoirs of her daughter Alimjonova Zukhar Hamidovna, Zulfiya was very modest. When Anna Akhmatova lived in Tashkent during the evacuation years, Hamid Olimjon brought her food and cakes when she was sick. He thanked and greeted Zulfiya and asked to go to the guest. Zulfiya did not dare to go to Anna Andreevna. But he translated the poems of the Russian poetess, very close to him and understandable, with such creative enthusiasm and inspiration. Zulfia unjustifiably placed Akhmatova and Tsvetaeva above her in terms of poetic talent. Zulfia's poems were translated into Russian by many great Russian poets. Among them are Semyon Lipkin, Svetlana Somova, Zoya Tumanova, Yulia Neuman. The daughter of an ordinary degrez saw national fame and recognition, but she always remained an amazingly humble, endlessly hardworking person. His restless heart did not rest for a moment, he was always on the road, in pursuit of news. We hope that Zulfiya's poetic observations and visions will be overshadowed by several generations and her work will serve as an example and inspiration for poets for many years to come.

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